

fRamework for safE, opEn, collaboratiVe And inclUsive digitisAtion and managemenT of cultural heritagE

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Table of Contents

Publishable summary.....	10
1 Introduction	11
2 Related work.....	11
2.1 <i>Ontologies</i>	12
2.1.1 <i>Ontology lookup services</i>	13
2.1.2 <i>Upper ontologies</i>	13
2.1.3 <i>CH data models and domain ontologies</i>	14
2.1.4 <i>CH context domain ontologies</i>	17
2.1.5 <i>IPR domain ontologies</i>	18
2.1.6 <i>User profile domain ontologies</i>	19
2.2 <i>Methodologies</i>	20
2.3 <i>Tooling</i>	20
2.4 <i>Ontology Mapping</i>	20
3 Methodology.....	22
3.1 <i>Linked Open Terms methodology</i>	22
3.1.1 <i>Ontology requirements specifications</i>	22
3.1.2 <i>Ontology implementation</i>	31
3.1.3 <i>Ontology publication</i>	32
3.1.4 <i>Ontology maintenance</i>	32
4 Results.....	32
4.1 <i>The Cultural Artefacts' Contextual Ontology (CACAO)</i>	32
4.1.1 <i>Physical artefact</i>	34
4.1.2 <i>Digital artefact</i>	34
4.1.3 <i>User</i>	35
4.1.4 <i>Context</i>	36
4.1.5 <i>Rights</i>	36
4.2 <i>CACAO-RS</i>	37
5 ARTKB.....	38
6 Ontology mapping	40
6.1 <i>Mapping Methodology</i>	40

6.2	<i>Mapping to DBPedia, Wikidata, and Europeana Data Model</i>	42
6.2.1	<i>DBPedia Ontology</i>	42
6.2.2	<i>Wikidata Ontology</i>	42
6.2.3	<i>Europeana Data Model</i>	42
6.3	<i>Mapping Results</i>	43
7	Conclusion & Future Work	44
	References	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: CIDOC-CRM simplified view	15
Figure 2: ODRL simplified view	19
Figure 3: CACAO overview	33
Figure 4 CACAO Physical Artefact.....	34
Figure 5 CACAO Digital Artefact	35
Figure 6 CACAO User	36
Figure 7: ODRL connection to CIDOC-CRM.....	37
Figure 8 Example of artwork instance in Knowledge Graph	39

List of Tables

Table 1 Functional requirements generated from D1.3.....	23
Table 2 Possible mappings of extracted terms to ontologies. The following prefixes are used: crm: http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/ , schema: https://schema.org/ , wiki: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/ , dct: http://purl.org/dc/terms/ , SKOS: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#	24
Table 3 Mapping of data sources to CIDOC-CRM	26
Table 4 Competency Questions	30
Table 5 Automatically generated mappings from CACAO to each target ontology	43
Table 6 Manually curated mappings from CACAO to each target Ontology	43

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full name
CACAO	Cultural Artefacts' Contextual Ontology
ccREL	Creative Commons Rights Expression Language
CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC	International Council for Documentation
DAML	DARPA Agent Markup Language
DOLCE	Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EKAW	European Knowledge Acquisition Workshop
ESWC	Extended Semantic Web Conference
FOAF	Friend Of A Friend Ontology
FRBR	Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records
FRBRoo	FRBR-object oriented
GLAM	Galleries Libraries Archives and Museums
ICOM	International Council of Museums
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISWC	International Semantic Web Conference
JWS	Journal of Web Semantics

K-CAP	International Conference on Knowledge Capture
LIDO	Lightweight Information Describing Objects
LOT	Linked Open Terms
LOV	Linked Open Vocabularies
MoMU	AG Culturele Instellingen Antwerpen/Erfgoed (<i>Modemuseum</i>)
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
ODK	Ontology Development Toolkit
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
OWL	Ontology Web Language
PROV-O	Provenance Ontology
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RO	Relations Ontology
SIG	Special Interest Group
SPK	Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz
SUMO	Suggested Upper Merged Ontology
SWJ	Semantic Web Journal
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Publishable summary

This document provides an overview of the methodology followed and the work on the Cultural Artefacts' Contextual Ontology (CACAO). The work is grounded in its relevance to both the project's objectives and the broader field of cultural heritage.

Firstly, the deliverable describes related work in the context of ontologies, ontology development methodologies, and ontology alignment techniques. Relevant upper-level and domain-specific ontologies are described, a high-level overview of representative ontology development methodologies is given, and ontology mapping techniques are described.

Secondly, it is discussed how the chosen methodology is applied for the development of the CACAO ontology. The first steps of this methodology, requirements specification and ontology implementation, are described in detail, touching on the different inputs that served as inspiration for the requirements, as well as an extensive description of how those inputs were translated to functional and non-functional requirements.

In addition, the ontology itself is explained, elaborating on the five most relevant classes, and its connection to the Open Digital Rights Language for the expression of Intellectual Property Rights. Each of the classes is described with example properties and given a place in the larger ontology.

Thirdly, the development of the ARTKB knowledge graph and its application in the project is described.

Lastly, we describe our ontology mapping efforts to align the CACAO ontology with other ontologies in and outside the domain.

By reading this deliverable, the readers will gain insights into the requirements process, the design decisions made, and the ontology's structure and use in representing cultural heritage data.

1 Introduction

The cultural heritage (CH) domain faces several challenges with regards to digitization, one of the most prominent being data heterogeneity, which leads to interoperability issues [1]. In an ideal scenario, a perfect, common, standardized data model enriched with semantics would be used by all CH institutions, ensuring that data is interoperable and understandable by all users, both human and artificial. With this ideal in mind, it is important to gather inputs from as many domain experts as possible to create consensus, satisfaction, and a growing community willing to use the ontology. To make such collaboration feasible, it is crucial to build in the open and make contributing to the ontology as easy as possible for domain experts.

In recent years, the CH sector has emphasized digitizing its collections. Digitization allows Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAMs) to improve the accessibility of their collections and support digital preservation, ensuring artefacts remain available even after physical deterioration. The CH domain increasingly leverages ontologies to achieve interoperability, enable rich semantic annotation, and facilitate metadata creation. However, to the best of our knowledge, current ontologies in the CH sector, e.g. CIDOC-CRM [2], EDM [3], do not fully capture the rich context of CH artefacts and the intellectual property rights (IPR) associated with their digital counterparts.

The Cultural Artefacts' Contextual Ontology (CACAO) is the ontology introduced by the REEVALUATE project, providing the backbone for the technical enablers that will be developed during the project. CACAO aims to address the gaps in historical contextualization and IPR by extending the widely recognized CH domain ontology CIDOC-CRM with other ontologies such as FOAF [4], ODRL [5], and schema.org [6]. This document aims to provide an overview of on-going work on CACAO. It outlines related research, the development methodology, a summary of the current ontology, and conclusions with directions for future work.

In the second version of this deliverable, the following work was added: we have further refined the properties and classes to be added to the CACAO ontology. For the expression of rights statements, a mapping between CIDOC-CRM and ODRL was established. In addition, a complementary vocabulary of rights statements was created, to provide a friction-less way to express commonly used rights statements with CACAO. The REEVALUATE KB was established by mapping Wikidata to CACAO. To establish connections to other initiatives, mappings between data models have been created automatically, and refined manually.

2 Related work

In this section, existing works are analyzed regarding the development of an ontology for context and IPR in the CH sector. It is imperative to reuse relevant, well-established ontologies, should there be such ontologies available. Additionally, when extending existing ontologies or defining a new one, we aim to follow an established ontology development methodology to ensure the outcome of the process is well-defined, structured and consistent. For these reasons, in section 2.1 existing ontologies in the CH field are analyzed, in section 2.2 we analyze ontology development methods, in section 2.3 tooling is briefly discussed, and in section 20 ontology mapping techniques are discussed.

2.1 Ontologies

An ontology is an explicit specification of a conceptualization [7]. It provides a shared vocabulary and way of representing information, ensuring that both humans and machines can understand and process it. An ontology serves multiple purposes. In the context of the REEVALUATE project, the following three are most important. Firstly, it enables interoperability of data between different systems, minimizing loss of meaning or accuracy when sharing data between parties. Secondly, it enables rich semantic annotation by linking metadata with precise descriptions, as well as relations between the different concepts. Lastly, ontologies allow advanced algorithms such as machine learning and natural language processing, to reason about the data.

Four types of ontologies exist, namely top-level, domain, task, and application ontologies [8].

- *Top-level ontologies, or upper ontologies*, describe very general concepts like space, time, matter, object, event, action, etc. which are agnostic of a domain [8], such as BFO [9] or DOLCE [10].
- *Domain ontologies* focus on a specific domain or area of knowledge [8], such as the CH domain, e.g., CIDOC-CRM, the clinical medicine domain, e.g., SNOMED CT [11] or the machine learning domain, e.g., MLSea [12].
- *Task ontologies* are similar to domain ontologies in the sense that they are focused on describing the vocabulary of a task [8], e.g. the Medical Action Ontology [13] or the Generic Task Ontology [14].
- *Application ontologies* are specialized ontologies that contain definitions specific to a particular application. They combine elements from both domain and task ontologies [8]. An example is given in [15].

Generally, top-level ontologies are intended to be reused and extended for a particular domain to create a *domain ontology* [16]. For that reason, an overview of top-level or upper ontologies is provided in section 2.1.2. In addition to the general, upper-level ontologies, several domains of interest were identified during the requirement gathering process described in section 3.1.1. The REEVALUATE framework proposes several enablers for the digitization lifecycle of an artefact such as the contextualisation and collaboration enabler. In the former, artefacts from the CH domain will be enriched with context by a human-driven and AI-driven process. In the latter, the enriched artefacts will be made available for reuse for users of the proposed marketplace. Therefore, ontologies related to the CH domain, context, intellectual property rights and user profiling, as well as general purpose ontologies, are required by the REEVALUATE platform.

For each of these domains, an overview of available ontologies is provided in section 2.1.3, 2.1.4, 2.1.5, and 2.1.6 respectively. To identify the relevant ontologies, ontology lookup services were used, which are described in section 2.1.1, and scientific publications were gathered using platforms such as Google Scholar¹ and dblp². Additionally, specific conferences, such as International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC), Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC), International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management (EKAW), International Conference on Knowledge Capture (K-CAP), and journals, e.g. Semantic Web Journal (SWJ), Journal of Web Semantics (JWS), were consulted.

¹ <https://scholar.google.com/>

² <https://dblp.org/>

2.1.1 Ontology lookup services

To find the most suitable ontologies for reuse in the context of our use-cases, it is important to have a broad view of those that are available. To provide such an overview several ontology lookup services attempt to catalogue the vast number of ontologies, either generally available or specific to a domain. During the review process, several of these ontology lookup services were used. In the following subsection, a short description of the services and their focus is given. The domain with the strongest use of ontologies is currently the biomedical domain, hence there is a strong bias to this domain in lookup services.

Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV)

LOV, available at <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov>, is a comprehensive ontology lookup service that catalogues and organizes a wide range of vocabularies and ontologies. It currently hosts vocabularies covering diverse domains such as metadata, industry, IoT, geography, environment, society, biology, government, and more.

OBO Foundry

The OBO (Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies) Foundry, available at <https://obofoundry.org/>, is a collaborative initiative that aims to develop a family of interoperable ontologies intended primarily for the biological and biomedical domains. A key feature is the OBO ontology principles³, which are intended as an evaluation metric for the ontologies submitted to the foundry. General-purpose ontologies such as PROV-O, the provenance ontology, can also be found in the OBO Foundry.

BioPortal

BioPortal is a comprehensive repository of biomedical ontologies. BioPortal is available at <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>. It provides a wider range of ontologies than the OBO Foundry. Similar to the OBO Foundry, it also provides access to more general-purpose ontologies.

Ontology Lookup Service (OLS)

Like the OBO Foundry and BioPortal, OLS, available at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4>, is a repository primarily focused on biomedical ontologies, but additionally provides access to general-purpose ontologies such as the Relations Ontology (RO)

2.1.2 Upper ontologies

In addition to achieving interoperability between the partners in REEVALUATE and the CH domain, it is just as important to achieve interoperability with other domains. This is especially apparent in the context of the emerging Common European Data Spaces⁴, to create inter data-space operability. As such, a mapping to an upper ontology will provide a solid foundation for the development of CACAO. This section provides a description of the three most prominent upper ontologies in the CH domain.

Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)

The Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) [9] is an upper ontology recommended by the OBO Foundry and is therefore widely adopted in the biomedical domain. However, its use is limited in the CH domain. It is used as the foundation for the NFDIcore ontology [17] which is in turn extended by the NFDI4Culture [18] ontology.

³ <https://obofoundry.org/principles/fp-000-summary.html>

⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

BFO distinguishes between universals and particulars, as well as occurrents and continuants—the latter indicating how particulars relate to time. These distinctions provide a clear separation of static and dynamic aspects of reality. Compared to other upper-level ontologies, BFO is relatively small in scope, as it focuses on high-level, general concepts. This minimalist approach maximizes broad applicability and avoids unnecessary complexity. It is also recognized as an International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standard⁵ and is available in OWL format [9].

Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering (DOLCE)

The Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering (DOLCE) [10] is an upper-level ontology developed in 2002/2003 and has remained stable since its initial release. As its name suggests, DOLCE finds its inspiration in cognitive and linguistics considerations [19]. Therefore, additional alignment efforts might be necessary when integrating with ontologies that have different foundational perspectives. DOLCE has been adopted in fields such as industrial engineering [19], and has served as a means to improve the CIDOC-CRM ontology [20] [21]. To the best of our knowledge, DOLCE is not used as a foundation for any CH domain ontologies. Like BFO, DOLCE is recognized as an ISO standard⁶. While it is not fully available in OWL format, some implementations exist. However, these implementations are re-engineered versions that do not fully represent the formalized ontology⁷ [10]. DOLCE is an ontology of particulars where the distinction is made between endurants, perdurants, and abstracts [22].

Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO)

The Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO) [23] is a comprehensive upper-level ontology that aims to provide a foundation for semantic integration across various domains. Developed through the merging of different ontology modules and theories, SUMO is organized in a hierarchical structure with "Entity" as the topmost concept. The ontology covers a wide range of areas, from abstract concepts to specific domains, and is formalized using the Standard Upper Ontology Knowledge Interchange Format (SUO-KIF) [24]. SUMO's structure allows for the integration of domain-specific ontologies, making it a versatile tool for knowledge representation and reasoning. However, its lack of a strict ontological commitment and some inconsistencies in its axiomatization pose challenges for its application in certain contexts in and outside of the CH domain. Despite these limitations, SUMO's comprehensive nature and its mapping to lexical resources like WordNet [25] make it a valuable resource for various applications in artificial intelligence, natural language processing, and information retrieval [26], [27], [28], [29].

2.1.3 CH data models and domain ontologies

CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM)

The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM) [20] was developed by the CIDOC CRM Special Interest Group (SIG), a committee of the International Council for Documentation (CIDOC), under the International Council of Museums (ICOM). It is a widely used ontology within the CH domain. While not officially classified as an upper ontology, CIDOC-CRM provides a high-level framework for organizing cultural heritage information. It is designed to be extended and specialized for specific use cases in the CH domain, such as documenting archaeological buildings [30]. At its highest level, CIDOC-CRM distinguishes between temporal entities, timespans, places, dimensions, persistent items, and spacetime volumes. The

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/74572.html>, last accessed 21/11/2024

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/78927.html>, last accessed 21/11/2024

⁷ <https://www.loa.istc.cnr.it/dolce/overview.html>, last accessed 21/11/2024

model structures information around events rather than static objects, making it a dynamic and process-oriented approach.

Figure 1: CIDOC-CRM simplified view

The core of the model revolves around describing how *crm:E39 Actor* (representing people, groups, or institutions) interacts with and creates various entities. These interactions are typically modelled as instances of *crm:E7 Activity* (or its subclasses). For instance, an *crm:E39 Actor* might carry out an *crm:E65 Creation* event (a subclass of *crm:E7 Activity*) that brings into existence an *crm:E73 Information Object* (such as a document, image, or dataset) or an *crm:E22 Human-Made Object* (a physical artefact). An *crm:E73 Information Object*, which is an identifiable immaterial item, can be the subject of *crm:E30 Right*. This class, *crm:E30 Right*, represents legal privileges such as copyright or ownership. The relationship is often established through the property *crm:P104 is subject to* (applies to), linking the *crm:E72 Legal Object* (a superclass of *crm:E73 Information Object*) to the *crm:E30 Right*. Furthermore, an *crm:E39 Actor* can hold or possess an *crm:E30 Right* over an *crm:E73 Information Object* or an *crm:E22 Human-Made Object* (as *E22* is also a subclass of *crm:E72 Legal Object*). This is typically expressed using properties like *crm:P75 possesses* (*is possessed by*) or *crm:P105 right held by* (*has right on*) connecting the *crm:E39 Actor* to the *crm:E30 Right*. Human-made objects (*crm:E22 Human-Made Object*) are physical items created through human activity, often detailed via production events (*crm:E12 Production*, a subclass of *crm:E7 Activity*), which in turn involve an *crm:E39 Actor*. These physical objects can also be the subject of *crm:E30 Right* held by *crm:E39 Actors*.

Furthermore, CIDOC-CRM is recognized as an ISO standard⁸. It is officially published through a specification document, which notes that the OWL file is a derivative. The version available in the OWL file [31] currently aligns with the latest iteration of the model (version 7.1.3).

Europeana Data Model (EDM)

The Europeana Data Model (EDM) [3] is the data model developed by Europeana⁹ and serves as the backbone for their repository of over 60 million CH artefacts. Europeana will form the heart of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). As such, its data model is a highly valuable resource for guaranteeing interoperability in the CH domain. It is published in the form of a specification document and has OWL files available. EDM defines 11 top-level classes, six of which, Agent, Event, Information Resource, Physical Thing, Place, and Time Span, are equivalent to classes defined in CIDOC-CRM and are mapped accordingly. The other five classes are Europeana Aggregation, Europeana Object, Non-Information Resource, Provided Cultural Heritage Object, and Web Resource.

edm:ProvidedCHO (Provided Cultural Heritage Object) is at the heart of EDM. This class represents the actual cultural object itself, e.g., a painting, book, manuscript, piece of music, or archaeological find. It is the subject of the metadata description. An *edm:WebResource* represents a digital file accessible on the web that is a representation of the *edm:ProvidedCHO*. This could be an image, a video, an audio file, a 3D model, or a textual document. There can be multiple *edm:WebResource* instances for a single *edm:ProvidedCHO*, for example, different image resolutions or formats, or different views of an object. To link the *edm:ProvidedCHO* to its digital representations and contextual information, EDM uses *ore:Aggregation*. This class, from the OAI-ORE (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange) [35] model, groups together all resources related to a single *edm:ProvidedCHO* as provided by a data contributor. It acts as a packaging for information about the object's digital presence and metadata. The *ore:Aggregation* connects the *edm:ProvidedCHO* (via *edm:aggregatedCHO*) to one or more *edm:WebResource* instances. Information about individuals, organisations, or other entities responsible for the creation, contribution, or different roles related to the *edm:ProvidedCHO* is represented by *edm:Agent*. An *edm:Agent* can be linked to the *edm:ProvidedCHO* or the *ore:Aggregation* through various properties (e.g., *dc:creator*, *dcterms:contributor*, *edm:hasMet*). *edm:Event* is a class in EDM that allows for the description of significant occurrences related to the lifecycle of the *edm:ProvidedCHO*, such as its creation, modification, or acquisition. The use of *edm:Event* in EDM provides a mechanism to encode such temporal and contextual information when available explicitly, linking *edm:Agents*, *edm:Places*, and *edm:TimeSpans* to the object's history. Rights information is handled primarily through the *edm:rights* property, typically associated with the *ore:Aggregation* and/or individual *edm:WebResources*, which is different from CIDOC-CRM where the *crm:E30 Right* class can be associated with a physical object (*crm:E22 Human-Made Thing*) as well. The value of *edm:rights* is usually a URI pointing to a standardised rights statement (e.g., from Creative Commons or RightsStatements.org), which describes what users can do with the digital object (*edm:WebResource*).

In addition, Europeana has several vocabularies available, for example, *edm:Agent*, which are mapped to entities available in, among others, Wikidata, ULAN, and DBpedia.

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/85100.html>, last accessed 21/11/2024

⁹ <https://www.europeana.eu/en>, last accessed 21/11/2024

EDM version 5.2.8 is the latest release of the data model and its definition was published in 2017. However, at the time of writing, the ontology lags two minor versions behind the specification document (version 5.2.6). For the development of a robust knowledge graph, the availability of an ontology is a primary requirement, making the reuse of EDM for this purpose less justifiable.

Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO)

Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO) [32] is an XML schema designed for harvesting and delivering metadata about museum objects. Similar to CIDOC-CRM, LIDO is maintained by the International Committee for Documentation (CIDOC)¹⁰, a committee of the International Council of Museums (ICOM). In fact, LIDO is a specific application of CIDOC-CRM. Consequently, LIDO relies heavily on CIDOC-CRM classes and adopts its event-centric approach.

Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR & FRBRoo)

Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) is an entity-relationship model for metadata concerning information objects. As its name implies, it is primarily used for bibliographic information. FRBR was developed concurrently with the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM). Efforts to align the two models resulted in FRBR Object-Oriented (FRBRoo) [33], an object-oriented extension of FRBR. FRBRoo incorporates the dynamic aspects of CIDOC-CRM into FRBR [34], effectively serving as an extension of CIDOC-CRM. The foundational concepts of the FRBR model are *Work*, *Expression*, *Manifestation*, and *Item*.

2.1.4 CH context domain ontologies

The Merriam-Webster dictionary defines *context* as “*the parts of a discourse that surround a word or passage and can throw light on its meaning*”¹¹. Given such a broad definition, many ontologies could be viewed as contributing to the modelling of context, depending on their purpose and scope. Hence, in many existing ontologies, context is often treated as a catch-all field, represented through optional, unstructured free-text annotations (e.g. [35], [36]). This approach, while flexible, limits the potential for systematic and interoperable contextual modelling.

Previous works have attempted to model context explicitly. These efforts are often domain-specific, focusing on areas such as intelligent and mobile environments [37], [38], and are therefore not directly applicable to cultural heritage. By contrast, large, open knowledge bases such as Wikidata [39] and DBpedia [40] offer broad, domain-agnostic data models in RDF format. Their structured representation of diverse information, combined with their wide applicability, makes them valuable resources for contextual information. For instance, the rich semantic links in these knowledge bases can provide contextual relationships that are relevant for modelling cultural heritage data.

Finally, “Getty Vocabularies” is an umbrella term for a list of vocabularies published and maintained by the Getty Research Institute and contains the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN), the Union List of Artist Names (ULAN), the Getty Iconography Authority (IA) and the Cultural Objects Name Authority (CONA).

¹⁰ <https://icom.museum/en/committee/international-committee-for-documentation/>

¹¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/context>, last accessed 21/11/2024

These vocabularies contain structured terminology for art, architecture, decorative arts, archival materials, visual surrogates, conservation, and bibliographic materials, providing a hierarchical structure among the included concepts.

The Getty Vocabularies provide rich, curated terminologies that are valuable for populating CH knowledge graphs with fine-grained data. In CH data modelling, such structured vocabularies are frequently utilised to provide specific typing for entities, for instance, by employing CIDOC-CRM's `crm:P2 has type` property to link an entity to an AAT term (e.g., `aat:300033618` for 'paintings (visual works)').

Furthermore, they can serve as an essential source for controlled values for various descriptive properties.

2.1.5 IPR domain ontologies

In the context of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Rights Expression Languages (REL) [41] offer a formal, machine-readable framework that expresses the terms and conditions under which intellectual property can be used, shared, or transferred. RELs are essential tools for managing and automating compliance with intellectual property rights, particularly in digital environments, where clear definitions of permissions and restrictions are crucial for content distribution.

Two of the most prominent RELs are the Creative Commons Rights Expression Language (ccREL) [42] and the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) [5].

Creative Commons Rights Expression Language (ccREL)

ccREL is structured around two main property types: work properties and license properties. Work properties describe the resource itself and include fields such as title and creator. License properties define the conditions of the license, categorizing them into Permissions, Restrictions, and Obligations [42]. Although ccREL is highly valuable for expressing Creative Commons (CC) licenses, it is focused on representing the CC licenses and thus lacks the fine-grained nature to express additional licenses or rights statements.

Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)

The ODRL Core Model is built around the Policy class, which encompasses Permissions, Prohibitions, and Duties. These components are associated with specific Parties, Assets, and Actions, allowing for a nuanced representation of rights and obligations within digital content distribution frameworks [5].

Figure 2: ODRL simplified view

Figure 2 provides a simplified view of the model. The central class is `odrl:Policy`, through which the rules (`odrl:Rule`) are expressed related to assets (`odrl:Asset`). Rules are correlated with actions `odrl:Action`. The action is either permitted, required, or prohibited depending on what subclass of `odrl:Rule` is used. Finally, `odrl:Party` can be used to express which parties are involved in a `odrl:Rule`, through the `odrl:assigner` and `odrl:assignee` properties, allowing for a nuanced representation of rights and obligations within digital content distribution frameworks [5]. ODRL provides a more generalised and extensible policy language framework beyond the specific licenses of Creative Commons. Its model of Policies, Assets, Rules (Permissions, Prohibitions, Duties), Actions, and Parties allows for more granular and complex rights statements to be constructed. Crucially, the W3C and European Commission’s recommendation for ODRL in the context of European Data Spaces strongly aligns with REEVALUATE’s aims and the broader ECCCH initiative, making ODRL a more strategic choice for interoperability in this context.

2.1.6 User profile domain ontologies

A recent systematic review of user profile ontologies identified a range of models for representing user information, including the General User Modeling Ontology (GUMO) [43], User Profile Ontology (UPO) [44], OntobUMf [45], Holistic Persona Ontology (HPO) [46], Persona Ontology (PO) [47], Grapple ontology [48], User Modelling Meta-ontology [49] and the Friend Of A Friend Ontology (FOAF)¹². These ontologies were evaluated as potential frameworks for user profile modelling, with the User Profile Meta-Ontology proposed as a unifying solution.

Despite the existence of OWL specification documents for these ontologies, the associated OWL files are no longer readily available, limiting their potential for reuse. An exception is the FOAF ontology, which thus serves as a valuable resource for representing user information.

¹² <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>, last accessed 22/11/2024

2.2 Methodologies

A wide range of development methodologies is available for designing and implementing ontologies. Five methodologies deemed most representative by the study are analysed in [50]. This systematic literature review concluded that, while these methodologies adopt different approaches, their conceptual steps are fundamentally similar. Specifically, these steps include:

1. Determining the domain and scope of the ontology
2. Implementation (of the ontology)
3. Evaluation (of the ontology)
4. Documentation and maintenance (of the ontology)

The specific methodologies may further subdivide these steps into smaller, more detailed components.

Although the systematic literature review does not explicitly mention it, the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology [51] aligns closely with these steps. The LOT methodology comprises:

1. Ontology requirements specification
2. Ontology implementation
3. Ontology publication
4. Ontology maintenance

In the LOT methodology, ontology evaluation is integrated into the implementation step.

2.3 Tooling

The biomedical domain faces similar challenges as the CH domain regarding data management and data integration. Specifically, data is heterogeneous, and domain experts' input is necessary throughout the entire lifecycle of ontology development. Additionally, it is noted that domain experts are often not trained in software engineering, making it more difficult for them to contribute to these ontologies [52].

The Ontology Development Kit (ODK) [52] is a toolkit for building, maintaining, and standardizing biomedical ontologies. It provides several standardized, customizable workflows and packages, readily available to execute locally or using automated workflows on common repository hosting services. Although ODK was developed for the biomedical domain, it attempts to address the root problems apparent in both the biomedical and CH domains, making it applicable to the REEVALUATE use-case. By utilizing repository hosting services, one can develop in public. Additionally, domain experts can provide their input in plain language using integrated issue trackers, lowering the barrier to contribution. Moreover, ODK not only makes it easier for less technical users to contribute but also reduces the burden on ontology engineers and more technically inclined contributors due to its automation capabilities.

2.4 Ontology Mapping

Ontology matching plays a central role in enabling semantic interoperability across heterogeneous knowledge sources. It refers to the process of identifying correspondences, also known as mappings or alignments, between semantically related entities (e.g., classes, properties) in different input ontologies. These mappings can be used for various downstream tasks, including ontology merging, data integration, query translation, and knowledge graph navigation.

By resolving terminological and conceptual differences between ontologies, ontology matching enables systems to interpret, query, and reason across diverse knowledge representations. For example, aligning domain-specific ontologies to general-purpose knowledge bases like DBpedia or Wikidata allows for enhanced information retrieval and cross-domain inference. Moreover, as the scale and diversity of ontological resources grow, automated or semi-automated ontology matching approach becomes increasingly critical to support scalable knowledge integration.

Existing works in ontology matching mainly focus on the techniques from lexical and structural heuristics to machine learning and large language models (LLMs). Evaluation campaigns such as the Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative (OAEI) have become standard benchmarks for comparing the performance of ontology mapping systems across diverse domains and tasks. In this context, the methods and tools selected in our work to align our domain ontology with external vocabularies are primarily from those that have demonstrated strong performance in recent OAEI tracks or are widely adopted in ontology matching works. In the following, we summarize representative ontology mapping tools. For each tool, we describe its methodological approach (e.g., lexical-based, LLM-based, etc.) and the scope of alignment (e.g., class-level matching, property-level matching).

AgreementMakerLight (AML) [53], [54], [55] AML is a long-standing ontology matching system that has been actively developed for over ten years, with consistent top-tier performance in the OAEI campaigns. AML can perform schema or instance mapping with a hybrid architecture that integrates lightweight techniques such as string similarity and synonym expansion with logic-based reasoning modules. It supports the flexible configuration of function, while the system primarily targets class-level mapping, it also supports property mapping, which can be enabled through its configurable options and the use of lexical similarity on property labels. From a development and usage perspective, AML is one of the most mature and well-maintained ontology mapping tools. Its source code is publicly available and frequently updated. Furthermore, AML provides both a command-line interface and a graphical user interface, improving its accessibility for users.

LogMap [56], [57] LogMap is a logic-based and scalable ontology matching system, designed to handle very large ontologies with rich axiomatization. Unlike most mapping systems that focus on lexical similarity, LogMap tightly integrates logic-based reasoning into the mapping process. Its core design includes mechanisms for on-the-fly unsatisfiability detection and repair, enabling the production of alignments that are logically coherent with respect to the merged ontologies. LogMap proceeds by first computing anchor mappings through lexical and structural indexing, including optional external lexicons (e.g., WordNet), and then iteratively expands and repairs mappings via a lightweight reasoning process. For reasoning, it uses a Horn-propositional encoding of class hierarchies and mappings, along with the Dowling-Gallier satisfiability algorithm. However, LogMap is mainly tailored for class-level matching; it does not support property or instance alignment. Moreover, it does not incorporate machine learning or large language models. LogMap remains one of the most cited ontology alignment systems in the logic-based category.

Matcha-DL [58] Matcha-DL is a supervised ontology matching system that builds on the AML and Matcha [59] frameworks to improve the alignment of ontologies through machine learning. While AML and Matcha rely on rule-based combinations of matching algorithms, Matcha-DL replaces these handcrafted strategies with a learned ranking model that is trained on partial reference alignments. It leverages confidence scores generated by multiple matchers (e.g., lexical, background knowledge, thesaurus-based) and uses them as features for a linear neural network. The model learns to rank candidate correspondences and outputs a

final alignment filtered by confidence thresholds and additional constraints for coherence and locality. However, its architecture is currently focused on class-level equivalence matching and requires partial ground-truth alignments for training, limiting its applicability in zero-shot scenarios or for aligning properties. Matcha-DL focuses on class-level mapping and instance-level mapping, does not support property-level mapping.

BERTMap [60] BERTMap is a BERT-based ontology mapping tool that introduces deep contextual semantic understanding into ontology matching. Unlike traditional systems that rely on string-based similarity and heuristic structures, BERTMap leverages transformer-based pre-trained language models to compute semantic similarity between concept labels. It supports both unsupervised and semi-supervised alignment modes. BERTMap begins by constructing synonym and non-synonym label pairs from the ontologies and any optional auxiliary sources. These pairs are used to fine-tune a pre-trained BERT model into a binary classifier. The system then performs mapping prediction using sub-word inverted indices to generate candidate mappings and computes confidence scores with the fine-tuned BERT classifier. BERTMap focuses primarily on class-level matching and does not provide support for property or instance alignment.

OntoAligner [61] OntoAligner is a modular, Python-based ontology alignment toolkit that integrates lightweight, retrieval-based, and large language model (LLM) approaches, aiming to provide both high alignment quality and extensibility. One of OntoAligner's key features is its modular architecture, which allows users to plug in custom encoders, matchers, post-processing modules, and evaluation metrics. Regarding mapping scope, OntoAligner supports class alignment so far.

While most reviewed tools focus primarily on class-level alignment, AML is the only tool that explicitly supports property-level mapping. Given our requirement to align both classes and properties, AML stands out as the most suitable candidate for our ontology mapping tasks.

3 Methodology

Here we describe how the selected ontology development methodology is applied to the REEVALUATE project. The requirement gathering process is described in section 3.1.1. In section 3.1.2, the ontology implementation choice is described and underpinned by an overview of current and foreseen problems related to development of and contributing to an ontology in the CH domain.

3.1 Linked Open Terms methodology

Due to its industrial applicability, the authors' previous positive experience with LOT, and its satisfactory overlap with the methodologies considered most representative in [50], the LOT methodology was selected for developing CACAO [62].

3.1.1 Ontology requirements specifications

Review & interview findings (D1.1 & D1.2)

The literature review in D1.1, as well as the output of the interviews and surveys of CH professionals in D1.2 provide valuable insights into gaps within the CH domain, such as lack of technical expertise and reliance on existing partnerships. From the perspective of specifying requirements for the ontology, we can consider these findings primarily from a non-functional standpoint. Specifically, we have extracted the following non-functional requirements, where RX stands for Requirement X:

R1 Ease of Contribution: Many CH institutions perceive themselves as falling behind in adopting the latest technological advancements due to limited funding, lack of technical expertise, or resistance to change within the organisation; therefore, it should be easy for non-technical users to contribute to the ontology.

R2 Accessibility and Openness: In the spirit of democratizing access to CH artefacts, it is only natural that the ontology should be as widely accessible as possible and developed openly.

R3 Comprehensive Documentation: The ontology should be well-documented to facilitate ease of use and adoption by users.

R4 Community Feedback and Consensus: Since CH institutions rely heavily on established partnerships, it is important to enable the broader community to provide feedback and reach consensus on the ontology's implementation.

User needs & usage scenarios (D1.3)

Deliverable D1.3 discusses Goals (G), Requirements (R), Obstacles (O), Needs (N), and Domain Hypotheses (D). In relation to the framework and technological enablers that will be developed in the REEVALUATE project. Goals are high-level objectives that are subdivided into smaller components: requirements and needs. Requirements are low-level tasks that need to be executed by the project’ enablers, while needs pertain to user-facing (front-end) aspects. A domain hypothesis is an assumed general truth about the domain. An obstacle is a barrier to achieving a goal.

With these definitions in mind, we should focus on requirements and needs during the user requirements phase. Each of the user requirements were analysed and the relevant ones were translated into functional or non-functional ontology requirements. The needs are analysed in a similar manner.

This analysis results in the following required components for the ontology:

Table 1 Functional requirements generated from D1.3

Class	Properties
User profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demographics - Affiliation - Interests
Digital artefact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing metadata - Source - Related artefacts - Context - IPR - Reuse restrictions - Image(s)/media

Additionally, the following requirements were extracted:

- R5** Solid descriptions
- R6** Follow W3C guidelines
- R7** Maximum reuse of existing ontologies
- R8** Language tags
- R9** Efficient querying (to reduce the ecological footprint)

Architectural schema & mock-ups (D1.5)

The architecture and mockups were created with consideration of the user needs and usage scenarios defined in D1.3. Nonetheless, we analyzed the D1.5 deliverable to identify any additional functional or non-functional requirements that might arise from the architecture, independent of the user needs and usage scenarios. No additional requirements were extracted from the proposed architecture (D1.5).

Gathered data sources (T2.1)

T2.1 is responsible for gathering the artefacts to be used in the REEVALUATE framework. REEVALUATE will run a number of pilots during the project's duration. As a result of these pilots, we have the privilege of working with four CH institutions, namely Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz (SPK), Olympiako Mouseio, AG Culturele Instellingen Antwerpen/Erfgoed (MoMU) and Fondazione Aquileia, and thus have access to real-life CH data. Thus, an additional requirement is defined:

- R10** fit all existing data shared by the institutions.

The data provided generally consists of images and relevant metadata. In some cases, 3D models are also provided. We analysed the preliminary results of T2.1 and additional data gathered from the partners to compile a list of ontology terms and properties. In the first phase, candidate terms from existing ontologies were mapped onto the extracted terms; this analysis is available in Table 2. In the second phase, a single candidate ontology, CIDOC-CRM, was selected to map the existing data and metadata too. Except for two properties, all the terms and properties extracted from the data sources were mappable to CIDOC-CRM. The mappings are available in Table 3.

Table 2 Possible mappings of extracted terms to ontologies. The following prefixes are used: crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>, schema: <https://schema.org/>, wiki: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/>, dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>, SKOS: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .

In Class	Possible mappings
Artefact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E18_Physical_thing ▪ schema: thing ▪ wiki: artificial object (Q16686448)
Identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E42_Identifier ▪ wiki: identifier (Q853614)
Type of object / classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E55_Type ▪ wiki: type (Q21146257)
Title	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E35_Title ▪ dct: title ▪ schema: title ▪ wiki: title (Q216353)
Repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ wiki:repository (Q108296843)
Place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E53_Place

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ schema: place ▪ wiki: geographic location (Q2221906) ▪ dct: location
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E16_Measurement ▪ wiki: measurement (Q12453)
Value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E60_Number ▪ schema:value ▪ wiki: numeric value (Q10388960)
Unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E58_Measurement_unit ▪ schema: unitText ▪ wiki: unit of measurement (Q47574)
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E5_Event ▪ wiki: occurrence (Q1190554) ▪ schema: event ▪ dct: event
Date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E61_Time_Primitive ▪ wiki: point in time (Q186408) ▪ schema: Date ▪ dct: date
Time span	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E52_Time-Span ▪ wiki: time interval (Q186081)
Material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E57_Material ▪ wiki: material (Q214609) ▪ schema: material
Actor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E39_Actor ▪ wiki: agent (Q24229398) ▪ schema: Person
Nationality (of the actor)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ schema:nationality ▪ wiki: nationality (Q231002)
Role (of the actor)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ schema:Role ▪ wiki: role (Q4897819)
Related work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ wiki: related match (Q39894604) ▪ SKOS: relatedMatch
Legal body	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E74_Group ▪ wiki: legal person (Q3778211)
Record	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm: E90_Symbolic_Object ▪ wiki: digital representation (Q42396623)
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E30_Right ▪ wiki: license (Q79719) ▪ schema: License ▪ dct: License
Resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ crm:E73_Information_Object

- wiki: information object (Q23698381)

Table 3 Mapping of data sources to CIDOC-CRM

	Original term	Subject	Predicate	Object
Digital Artefact	Digital Artefact	Digital Artefact	a (rdf:type)	E73_Information_Object
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Type		P2_Has_Type	E55_Type
	Note		P3_has_note	rdfs:Literal
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
	Rights		P104_is_subject_to	E30_Right
	Holding organisation		P50_has_current_keeper	E39_Actor
	Digital representation of ..		P67_refers_to	E1_CRM_Entity
	Related artefacts		P130_shows_features_of	E70_Thing
	Legal		P104_is_subject_to	E30_Right
	Image(s)		P138i_has_representation	E36_Visual_Item
Physical Artefact	Physical artefact	Physical artefact	a	E22_Human-Made_Object
	Type		P2_Has_Type	E55_Type
	Description		schema:description	rdfs:Literal
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
	Title		P102_has_title	E35_Title
	Related artefact		P130_shows_features_of	E70_Thing
	Current (permanent) location		P54_has_current_permanent_location	E53_Place

	Part (of resource, resource = digital artefact)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P106_is_composed_of - P46_is_composed_of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E90_Symbolic_Object - E18_Physical_Thing
	Subject (object name)		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Has current location (most specific location)		P55_has_current_location	E53_Place
	Creator		P94i_was_created_by	E65_Creation
		E65_Creation	P14_carried_out_by	E39_Actor
	Date (of creation)	E65_Creation	P4_has_time-span	E52_Time-Span
	Medium		P2_Has_Type	E57_Material
	Measurements of the object		P39i_was_measured_by	E16_Measurement
		E16_Measurement	P40_observed_dimension	E54_Dimension
		E54_Dimension	P90_has_value	rdfs:Literal
		E54_Dimension	P91_has_unit	E58_Measurement_Unit
	Publisher/Holding institution		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P49_has_former_or_current_keeper - P50_has_current_keeper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E74_Group
	Note		P3_has_note	rdfs:literal
	Condition		P44_has_condition	E3_Condition_State
Place	Place	Place	a	E53_Place
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
	Falls within		P89_falls_within	E53_Place

Rights	Rights	Rights	a	E30_Right
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
Appellation	Appellation	Appellation	a	E41_Appellation
	Content		P190_has_symbolic_content	rdfs:Literal
Actor	Actor	Actor	a	E21_Person
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Nationality		schema:nationality	rdfs:literal
	Role		schema:Role	rdfs:Literal
	Birth		P98i_was_born	E67_Birth
	Death		P100i_died_in	E69_Death
Legal body	Legal body	Legal body	a	E74_Group
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
Event	Event	Event	a	E5_Event
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Type		P2_Has_Type	E55_Type
	Location		P7_took_place_at	E53_Place
	Carried out by		P11_had_participant	E39_Actor
Resources (image/video/text/ audio/...)	Resource	Resource	a	E73_Information_O bject
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation

	Type		P2_Has_Type	E55_Type
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
	Date of creation		P94i_was_created_by	E65_Creation
		E65_Creation	P4_has_time-span	E52_Time-Span
		E52_Time-Span	P79_beginning_is_qualified_by	rdfs:Literal
		E52_Time-Span	P80_end_is_qualified_by	rdfs:Literal
	Holding organisation		P105_right_held_by	E74_Group
	Rights		P104_is_subject_to	E30_Right
Repositories	Repository	Repository	a	E78_Curated_Holding
	Name		P1_is_identified_by	E41_Appellation
	Location		P54_has_current_permanent_location	E53_Place
	Preferred identifier		P48_has_preferred_identifier	E42_Identifier
	Has rights		P75_possesses	E30_Right

Data management plan (D6.3)

The data management plan (D6.3) provides insight into different types of software licenses. It distinguishes between copyleft, permissive, and public domain licenses. Various licenses such as the GNU General Public License [63], the MIT License [64], and Creative Commons licenses [65] are available to specify the rights associated with these license types. Additionally, a custom license can be defined if the licensor's needs are not covered by any pre-existing licenses.

This analysis leads to the following requirements:

- R11** Ability to specify one of the open-source licenses.
- R12** Ability to specify a Creative Commons (CC) license.
- R13** Ability to indicate if something belongs to the public domain.
- R14** Ability to specify a custom license.

Definition of context

It is important to understand what the broader CH community means when referring to context. To this end, discussions were organized with the pilot partners in the project, where each partner provided their input separately. These inputs were then consolidated into common requirements.

Based on the inputs from the pilot partners, we have identified several key requirements for the ontology:

R15 Relevant Domain: The ontology should specify the domain, or category, to which each artefact belongs.

R16 Relation to Historical Events: It should capture the artefact's connection to significant historical events, highlighting its historical importance.

R17 Social Significance: The ontology should represent the artefact's relevance to social movements and its impact on society.

R18 Religious Significance: It should include information about the artefact's association with religious movements and its spiritual importance.

R19 Cultural Significance: The ontology should address the artefact's role in cultural movements, reflecting its influence on cultural development.

R20 Political Significance: It should reflect the artefact's connection to political movements and its significance in political history.

R21 Economic Significance: The ontology should encompass the artefact's impact on economic history, including its role in economic developments.

R22 Meaning of Material: There should be provisions for open-text descriptions that explain the significance of the materials used in the artefact.

R23 Meaning of Shapes: The ontology should capture the symbolic meanings associated with the shapes present in the artefact.

R24 Link to Other Artefacts: It should enable linking the artefact to other related artefacts, facilitating a network of connected cultural heritage items.

These requirements aim to ensure that the ontology comprehensively represents the contextual dimensions of cultural heritage artefacts, thereby enhancing understanding and accessibility for users.

Competency questions

In this section, for each of the functional requirements, competency questions are defined. An overview can be found in Table 4.

Table 4 Competency Questions

Functional Requirement	Competency Questions
R10 fit all existing data shared by the institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the location of the artefact? - What are the dimensions of the artefact? - Who holds the right of this artefact? - What resources are available for a distinct artefact?

	- Which digital artefact is a representation of a distinct physical artefact
R11 Ability to specify one of the open-source licenses	- Is there an open-source license specified for a distinct artefact? - What artefacts are available under a distinct open-source artefact?
R12 Ability to specify a Creative Commons (CC) license	- Is there a Creative Commons license specified for a distinct artefact? - What artefacts are available under a distinct Creative Commons artefact?
R13 Ability to indicate if something belongs to the public domain	- Does a distinct artefact belong to the public domain? - Which artefacts belong to the public domain?
R14 Ability to specify a custom license.	- Under which custom license is a distinct artefact available? - What are the duties related to a license? - What are the requirements related to a license? - What are the prohibitions related to a license?
R15 Relevant Domain	- What is the domain to which an artefact belongs? - What domains are defined within the ontology's structure? - What artefacts are classified in this domain?
R16 Relation to Historical Events	- What historical events are relevant to a given artefact? - What artefacts are relevant to a given historical event?
R17 Social Significance	- To what social movement is this artefact relevant? - Which social movements are relevant to this knowledge base?
R18 Religious Significance	- To what religious movement is this artefact relevant? - Which religious movements are relevant to this knowledge base?
R19 Cultural Significance	- To what cultural movement is this artefact relevant? - Which cultural movements are relevant to this knowledge base?
R20 Political Significance	- To what political movement is this artefact relevant? - Which political movements are relevant to this knowledge base?
R21 Economic Significance	- How is this artefact economically relevant?
R22 Meaning of Material	- What is the significance or symbolism of materials documented?
R23 Meaning of Shapes	- What is the meaning of shapes present on a distinct artefact?
R24 Link to Other Artefacts	- To what other artefacts is a distinct artefact related?

3.1.2 Ontology implementation

To implement the ontology, the ODK toolkit was used in combination with GitHub¹³ and Protégé¹⁴. Using ODK, terms from external ontologies are imported into the ontology-edit file, which can then be edited using Protégé. After the desired edits are saved, the update is pushed to GitHub. When a new release of the ontology is ready, an automatic workflow is run to create the desired output files, available at <https://github.com/REEVALUATE/CACAO/tree/main>, after which a GitHub release is created.

To request new terms or propose changes to the ontology, GitHub's integrated issue tracker can be used, by creating an issue or a pull request with implemented changes. This will maximize the outreach of the ontology while facilitating the acquisition of users' feedback that will help in evolving the ontology.

¹³ <https://github.com/>

¹⁴ <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

3.1.3 Ontology publication

The ontology files are hosted under a GitHub pages website (<https://reevaluate.github.io/cacao-ontology/index-en.html>). A w3id identifier (<http://w3id.org/cacao>) has been minted as a permanent identifier to the ontology and its related files. Finally, an ODK workflow is used to provide documentation for technical and non-technical users to be able to contribute to the ontology (<https://reevaluate.github.io/CACAO/>).

3.1.4 Ontology maintenance

Issues and additional requirements that were not initially identified can be communicated to the maintainers through GitHub issues. All contributions to the ontology can be suggested through a pull request on the GitHub repository.

4 Results

In the results section, the current implementation of the CACAO ontology is described. Firstly, the ontology is explained from a high-level perspective, after which subsequent sections explain in more detail the five major parts of the ontology.

4.1 The Cultural Artefacts' Contextual Ontology (CACAO)

Because of its widespread use in the CH domain, as well as its availability as an OWL formalization, CIDOC-CRM was chosen as the foundation for the CACAO ontology. Using all the requirements gathered, classes and properties that were deemed relevant were imported from CIDOC-CRM. The definitions of these terms can be found in the official documentation¹⁵. When the label of a class starts with 'E' or a property label starts with 'P', this indicates that the class or property is imported from CIDOC-CRM.

The ontology is based around five central concepts:

- The physical artefact
- The digital artefact
- The user (of the marketplace, for example)
- Context
- Rights

In this ontology, a digital artefact is the digitized representation of a physical artefact, and context is attached to the digital artefact. Both the digital and physical artefacts are subject to rights, which are held by high-level actors, including users and institutions. A user is interested in certain digital artefacts, events, and movements; events can, in turn, be connected to specific artefacts. CACAO is illustrated in **Error!**
Reference source not found..

¹⁵ <https://cidoc-crm.org/Version/version-7.1.3>

Figure 3: CACAO overview

4.1.1 Physical artefact

The physical artefact, which is directly mapped to CIDOC CRM's E22_Human-Made_Object, is illustrated in Figure 4.

The concept of the physical artefact encompasses information about its physical attributes, such as location, dimensions, and material. A physical artefact is identified using classes like *E41_Appellation*, *E35_Title*, and *E42_Identifier*. The condition, category, and material of the object are described using classes such as *E3_Condition_State*, *E55_Type*, and *E57_Material*, respectively. Rights statements can be expressed using the *E30_Right* class. In addition, the current physical holder, likely a CH institute, is expressed as a *39_Actor*.

Figure 4 CACAO Physical Artefact

4.1.2 Digital artefact

The digital artefact, which is directly mapped to *E73_Information_Object*, is illustrated in Figure 5.

The digital artefact represents any digital format of the physical artefact and is related to it through the property *P62i_is_depicted_by*. It can comprise a multitude of *E90_Symbolic_Objects*, each representing a different digital resource such as an image, video, 3D object scan, audio recording or even another Digital Artefact. Additionally, for provenance purposes, the creation of a digital artefact can be described using

E65_Creation. A digital artefact relates to events using the *P12i_was_present_at* property and can have reference to other entities using the *P67_refers_to* and *P129_is_about* properties. The use of which will become apparent in section 4.1.4 on context.

Figure 5 CACAO Digital Artefact

4.1.3 User

The user is a specialization of *E21_Person* and, consequently, a further specialization of *E39_Actor*. This implies that a user can hold rights regarding any legal object.

Figure 6 CACAO User

In this context, legal objects are the digital and physical artefacts, although our focus is on the digital. To align with the requirements of the marketplace as well as the recommendation system, the user's name, age (via birth and death dates), and identifier (e.g., ORCID) can be expressed using instances of reused CIDOC-CRM classes such as E67_Birth, E69_Death, and E41_Appellation. Additionally, the user's nationality, organisation, and interests can be expressed using instances and properties of the FOAF ontology. The organisation of the user can be used to assess their credibility.

4.1.4 Context

Based on the gathered requirements, several classes are defined. To model the historical context, *Historical Event* is defined as a subclass of *E5_Event*, while *Social Movement*, *Cultural Movement*, *Political Movement*, *Religious Movement*, and other movements discussed earlier are defined as subclasses of *E28_Conceptual_Object*. Using these classes, context can be added to digital artefacts by employing, for example, the property *P12_occurred_in_the_presence_of*, where a Historical Event is related to a digital or physical artefact, or *P67_refers_to* when referring to one of the movements.

4.1.5 Rights

In the context of the European data space initiatives, the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) is used to describe usage conditions. Additionally, the Creative Commons (CC) ontology can be used to express CC licenses and usage conditions. The essence of ODRL is the expression of policies through combinations of *Duty*, *Permission*, and *Prohibition*. CC licenses are expressed as combinations of *Requirement*, *Permission*, and *Prohibition*. Clearly, ODRL and CC adopt a similar approach in modelling usage policies. Therefore, we have chosen ODRL for IPR management in CACAO due to its backing from the European Union. ODRL uses the *Policy* class to define anything related to rights. *Policy* is related to *Permissions*, *Duties*, and *Prohibitions* through properties with the names *permission*, *obligation*, and *prohibition* respectively. These policies are then related to an *Asset* which is mapped onto a *E72_Legal_Object* in CIDOC-CRM. Both *Physical Artefact* and *Digital Artefact* are subclasses of *E72_Legal_Object*.

To extend CIDOC-CRM with ODRL, we look for classes and properties that are similar or equivalent and map them. The relevant subset of classes and properties of CIDOC-CRM is defined by narrowing its scope to the scope of ODRL, namely rights and licenses. Specifically, `crm:E72 Legal Object`, `crm:E30 Right` and `crm:E39 Actor` were identified as relevant for this topic. The importance of `crm:E72 Legal Object` and `crm:E39 Actor` is further emphasized as they are the only classes that are connected with `crm:E30 Right` through direct properties.

As ODRL uses the `odrl:Policy` class as a central point to capture all information associated with the expressed license, it is connected to `crm:E30 Right` using a new property `cacao:expressedBy`, with the idea of specifying the relevant right, using `odrl:Policy`. `crm:E72 Legal Object` comprises all items to which `crm:E30 Right` can be applied, hence it makes sense to map it to `odrl:Asset` as this is the same relation that is defined between `odrl:Asset` and `odrl:Policy`. As `crm:E72 Legal Object` has a broader definition than `odrl:Asset`, the ODRL class is mapped as a subclass of the CIDOC-CRM class. Finally, instances of `crm:E39 Actor` possess (`crm:P75 possesses`) the rights related to a `crm:E72 Legal Object`, which is equivalent to the `odrl:assigner` and `odrl:assignee` property between `odrl:Party` and `odrl:Policy`. Similar to the relation between `crm:E72 Legal Object` and `odrl:Asset`, `crm:E39 Actor` has a broader definition than `odrl:Party` and as such, the latter becomes a subclass of the former. An additional mapping is made between subclass `crm:E74 Group` and `odrl:PartyCollection`. Figure 7 shows the mappings made between CIDOC-CRM classes and equivalent ODRL classes.

Figure 7: ODRL connection to CIDOC-CRM

4.2 CACAO-RS

To put the connection between ODRL and CIDOC-CRM into practice, we defined the CACAO Rights Statements (CACAO-RS). CACAO-RS is a vocabulary that contains common rights statements, expressed using ODRL and directly usable in the CACAO ontology.

To ensure the CACAO Rights Vocabulary (CACAO-RS) enables expression of the rights that are most commonly used and are relevant for the broader CH domain, the Europeana Rights Statements¹⁶ were used to provide an initial selection. Included are six Creative Commons Licenses, two Creative Commons tools, and six out of the twelve Rights Statements from RightStatements.org¹⁷

As mentioned in section 36, a rights statement is expressed using an *odrl:Policy*. In the *odrl:Policy*, permissions, obligations, and prohibitions are expressed using *odrl:actions*. The ODRL ontology contains 51 different actions, two of which are generic and express the combination of other actions, *odrl:use* and *odrl:transfer*. To maintain fine-grained control, these actions are avoided when creating CACAO-RS.

First, we need to interpret the license texts. To do so, several keywords or topics such as "distribute", "remix", and "adapting the license" are extracted and expressed using the available actions. In almost all cases, one keyword or term encompasses many actions and can be mapped onto another term or keyword. Using this simplification, it becomes trivial to express the rights statements.

A notable exception is the In Copyright - Educational Use Permitted (InC-EDU 1.0) rights statement, which cannot be expressed merely with actions. This statement states that general use, modification, and sharing are allowed for educational use only, meaning that the permissions themselves are restricted. Such restrictions can be expressed using *odrl:Constraint*. An *odrl:Constraint* consists of a *odrl:leftOperand*, an *odrl:operator*, and an *odrl:rightOperand*.

5 ARTKB

ARTKB is the knowledge graph that provides the semantic basis for the enablers, developed in REEVALUATE. Using CACAO as the centralised data model, it serves as a database for integrating data from the involved CH institutes. This section outlines the construction process of the RDF-based knowledge graph in the domain of CH.

The pipeline comprises multiple stages, beginning with the processing of Wikidata and culminating in the generation of an RDF graph containing knowledge about artworks, artists, and related cultural entities. The process begins with Wikidata¹⁸, which has been utilised as the primary data source for creating the knowledge graph. Due to the vast size of Wikidata and the great variety of domains it represents, identifying and selecting the entities relevant to the artistic domain is a key challenge.

This is addressed through a combination of SPARQL queries and scripted filtering rules that extract entities related to artists, artworks, museums, movements, and genres.

Given that the focus of the knowledge graph is on relevant artefacts for the pilot partners in the project, like fashion-related artworks or archaeological, the entities related to artists, artworks, and museums are further narrowed down to those associated with these specific subdomains.

This filtering process yields a curated subset of Wikidata entities that are thematically aligned with the REEVALUATE project use case, thereby significantly reducing the volume of data to be processed.

Following the filtering phase, the curated dataset is transformed into RDF triples.

¹⁶ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/available-rights-statements>, last accessed 5/06/2025

¹⁷ <https://rightsstatements.org/en/>

¹⁸ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

For each Wikidata entity in the subset, a predefined selection of properties is retained and semantically aligned with the classes and properties defined in the CACAO ontology.

The specific set of retained properties depends on the nature of the entity—whether it represents a physical artefact, an artist, or a museum. To preserve traceability and facilitate integration with the source dataset, the original Wikidata URIs are reused as identifiers within the resulting RDF graph.

In addition to the core entities, several custom namespaces have been introduced to provide representations for specific concepts not directly modelled in Wikidata.

Temporal events such as births, deaths, and artefact productions are assigned unique identifiers and represented within the *w3id.org/cacao/vocab/event* namespace.

Images of physical artefacts, which are hosted on Wikimedia Commons¹⁹ (a Wikimedia project dedicated to the storage and distribution of media files) are treated as digital artefacts within the RDF graph.

These are modeled as distinct entities, assigned unique identifiers in the *w3id.org/cacao/vocab/digital-artefact* namespace, and explicitly linked as digital representations of the corresponding physical artefact.

The resulting RDF graph is loaded into an instance of GraphDB²⁰, a semantic graph database that exposes a public SPARQL endpoint, enabling users to explore the graph through structured queries. Figure 8 shows how an artwork entity is represented in the knowledge graph and its relationship with other entities.

Figure 8 Example of artwork instance in Knowledge Graph

The developed knowledge graphs will serve as storage for the artefacts and their metadata, together with their digitised version. It will also be the common contact point for all the semantic management enablers developed in WP2. Each of them will handle a different modality for the digitised version of an artefact (i.e.

¹⁹ https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Main_Page

²⁰ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com>

image, text or audio) but all of them will provide rich contextual information already compliant with the CACAO ontology and ready to be stored in the knowledge graph once their correctness has been confirmed. Lastly, ARTKB will serve as the basis for the information retrieval and recommendation systems in WP3.

6 Ontology mapping

This section presents our approach to aligning the CACAO ontology with external ontologies, including DBpedia, Wikidata, and the Europeana Data Model. The objective of this alignment is to facilitate semantic interoperability and link cultural heritage artefacts from ARTKB described in CACAO with external knowledge bases. Section 6.1 details the general methodology adopted for performing the mappings, including tool selection and configuration. Section 6.2 describes how the mapping process was applied to each target ontology. Section 6.3 summarizes the mapping results, including quantitative coverage and observations across class- and property-level correspondences.

6.1 Mapping Methodology

To establish reliable mappings between CACAO and external ontologies, we began by applying the various ontology matching systems introduced in Section 2.4 to align CACAO with DBpedia. This initial step allowed us to evaluate the performance of the tools via the alignment outputs. Based on alignment coverage and correctness, we selected AgreementMakerLight (AML) as the most suitable mapping system for our needs. We subsequently used AML to align CACAO with DBpedia, Wikidata, and the Europeana Data Model (EDM). All automatically generated mappings were then manually reviewed to filter out incorrect alignments and complement missing ones, ensuring high-quality semantic correspondences.

We selected AML for two main reasons. First, it consistently outperformed other tools in terms of the number of matched entities during our experiments. Second, while most other runnable systems supported only class-level alignment, AML was the only tool in our evaluation that also supported property-level matching, which is essential for the CACAO ontology. AML is a lightweight ontology matching system that supports a wide range of matching techniques, including lexical, structural, and background knowledge-based strategies. It is configurable via a simple configuration file that allows fine-grained control over individual components. For instance, we can enable or disable translation, specify sources of background knowledge, choose among multiple lexical and structural matchers, and control selection. Our configuration was finalized through iterative testing on the CACAO–DBpedia alignment and is as follows:

- `use_translator=false`
 - Controls whether entity labels are translated to a common language prior to matching. Options include *true*, *false*, and *auto*. We disabled it (*false*) because CACAO and the target ontologies primarily use English.
- `bk_sources=all`
 - Specifies which background knowledge sources to use. Possible values are *none*, *all*, or a *list of file names*. We used *all* to maximize lexical matching coverage through external ontologies like WordNet.
- `word_matcher=maximum`

- Defines how to compute the name similarity through a weighted Jaccard index of the words in the Lexicon entries of ontology entities of any entity type. Options include *by_class*, *by_name*, *average*, *maximum*, *minimum*, *none*, and *auto*. We selected maximum to preserve the strongest lexical similarity.
- `string_matcher=auto`
 - Specifies the strategy for string-level similarity between the Lexicon entries of ontology entities of any entity type. Options include *global*, *local*, and *auto*. The global option compares full names, the local option compares substrings, and the auto option lets AML choose heuristically. We used auto for adaptive behavior.
- `string_measure=ISub`
 - Determines the specific string similarity algorithm. Options include *ISub*, *Levenshtein*, *Jaro-Winkler*, and *Q-gram*. We chose *ISub* for its strong performance on cultural heritage ontologies.
- `struct_matcher=auto`
 - Controls whether and how structural information (e.g., class hierarchies) is used. Choices include *ancestors*, *descendants*, *average*, *maximum*, *minimum*, *none*, and *auto*. We used auto to let AML optimize this choice.
- `match_properties=true`
 - Enables property-level matching when set to true. This is crucial for aligning CACAO's object and data properties with external vocabularies.
- `selection_type=auto`
 - Specifies the alignment selection strategy. Options include *strict*, *permissive*, *hybrid*, *none*, and *auto*. We relied on auto to balance precision and recall.
- `repair_alignment=true`
 - When true, AML attempts to repair logical inconsistencies (e.g., cycles or disjoint violations) in the final alignment. We enabled this to improve semantic coherence.

Following the automatic alignment process, we conducted a thorough manual validation phase. Each generated correspondence was inspected to verify its correctness based on the semantics of both CACAO and the target ontology. Incorrect alignments were discarded and missing but semantically valid alignments were added manually. This hybrid methodology allowed us to ensure both broad coverage and high accuracy of the final mappings.

6.2 Mapping to DBPedia, Wikidata, and Europeana Data Model

We introduce the three external ontologies to which we aligned the CACAO ontology using AML. We describe the source and format of each target ontology and explain how we constructed or obtained them for our alignment tasks. As source ontology, we used the full CACAO ontology²¹.

6.2.1 DBPedia Ontology

The DBpedia ontology provides a general-purpose schema for describing encyclopedic knowledge extracted from Wikipedia. It is widely adopted for structured knowledge representation. In our work, we used the standard version of the DBpedia ontology²² as one of the target ontologies. The ontology is provided directly in OWL RDF/XML format and requires no transformation for compatibility with AML.

6.2.2 Wikidata Ontology

Unlike DBpedia, Wikidata does not publish a dedicated OWL ontology. Instead, its knowledge structure is encoded via Wikidata items (entities with Q-identifiers) and properties (P-identifiers), expressed in RDF using the Wikidata ontology namespace (wikidata.org/ontology#). However, this structure lacks an explicitly downloadable OWL schema.

To construct a usable target ontology from Wikidata for AML, we queried the Wikidata SPARQL endpoint²³ to extract a curated subset of classes and properties relevant to cultural heritage. Specifically:

- For properties, we retrieved all entities that are instances of *wikibase:Property*, including their labels and descriptions.
- For classes, we queried for all items that are subclasses (via `wdt:P279*` which represents the subclass of) of the item Q210272 (“cultural heritage”) and collected their `rdfs:label` and optional `schema:description`. This transitive subclass traversal ensured coverage of relevant cultural types such as paintings, manuscripts, and monuments.

We then converted the retrieved metadata into OWL class and property declarations using a custom Python script based on the `rdflib` library. The final constructed ontology was serialized in RDF/XML format for compatibility with AML.

6.2.3 Europeana Data Model

The EDM²⁴ is a domain-specific ontology designed for aggregating and describing digital representations of cultural heritage objects. It is used by the Europeana initiative to unify metadata across European galleries, libraries, archives, and museums. From that perspective, Europeana initiatives such as the list of rights statements and their on-going work like the vocabularies of entities, places, topics and time periods are considered for mappings to our ontology and knowledge graph. This ontology is published in RDF/XML and provides a consistent structure for representing objects, aggregations, contextual entities, and rights information, making it suitable as a target for aligning CACAO’s concepts.

²¹ <https://github.com/REEVALUATE/CACAO/blob/main/cacao-full.owl>

²² <http://150.146.207.114/lode/source?url=http://dief.tools.dbpedia.org/server/ontology/dbpedia.owl>

²³ <https://query.wikidata.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.europeana.eu/schemas/edm/rdf/edm.owl>

6.3 Mapping Results

In this section, we present the initial results produced by AML and the final alignments after manual verification. Our report focuses on the number of classes and properties successfully mapped between CACAO and each of the three target ontologies: DBpedia, Wikidata, and the EDM.

The first stage of our alignment involved applying AML with the configuration described in Section 6.1. **Table 5** summarizes the raw alignment output, reporting the number of mapped classes and properties identified by AML for each target ontology.

Table 5 Automatically generated mappings from CACAO to each target ontology

	DBpedia	Wikidata	EDM
Class	33	10	20
Property	46	75	27

Following the automated alignment, each mapping was reviewed manually to verify its semantic correctness. During this process, inaccurate mappings were removed and missing correspondences were added based on human interpretation and domain expertise. The resulting alignments provide a more reliable foundation for downstream reasoning and data integration. **Table 6 Manually curated mappings from CACAO to each target Ontology** presents the updated mapping statistics after manual curation.

Table 6 Manually curated mappings from CACAO to each target Ontology

	DBpedia	Wikidata	EDM
Class	33	4	20
Property	33	41	18

While the initial alignment covered 33 classes and 46 properties from DBpedia, the curated results were reduced to 33 classes and 33 properties. This reduction reflects the removal of mappings that, although lexically similar or structurally plausible, were semantically incompatible upon closer inspection. The current automatically generated mappings already cover all possible alignments, thus we do not add new mappings. Several examples illustrate the main issues behind these removals. For instance, the mapping between `odrl:target` and `dbpedia:targetAirport` was excluded because, despite similar labels, the former refers to the target of a policy or rule, whereas the latter refers to a physical airport destination, thus they are two entirely unrelated concepts. Similarly, the alignment of `odrl:action` with `dbpedia:hasJunctionWith` was eliminated due to a complete domain mismatch, where `odrl:action` is a conceptual property in rights expression languages and `dbpedia:hasJunctionWith` is a geographic property linking canals. In other cases, alignments were kept after modifying their alignment relation. For example, the mapping between `foaf:interest` and `dbpedia:mainInterest` was retained after changing the relation from equivalent to `subPropertyOf`, as both refer to an interest even though `foaf:interest` is broader in scope.

For Wikidata, a substantial number of incorrect alignments were identified and subsequently removed. In particular, many misalignments were caused by lexical ambiguity, for example, aligning `foaf:interest` with P5899 (interest rate), or `odrl:target` with P533 (military target), both of which represent fundamentally different semantics. As a result of this curation process, the number of aligned classes decreased from 10 to 4, and properties from 75 to 41. Similarly, the properties in the EDM alignments are also reduced from 28 to 18. These refined mappings better reflect the intended semantics of the source ontology.

7 Conclusion & Future Work

This document has presented an overview of the CACAO ontology, focusing on physical and digital artefacts, rights, context, and users. We analyzed related work, specified requirements through the LOT methodology, and implemented and published the ontology. In addition, we created a knowledge graph that contains data compliant with the CACAO ontology, and mapped other ontologies in the domain to our ontology.

The main benefits of the CACAO ontology include:

1. **A Uniform, Consistent Data Model:** Providing interoperability among the REEVALUATE project's partners and CH institutions outside the project that are willing to use the ontology, as well as a more semantically rich representation of data due to the ability to express relations through class-specific properties.
2. **Preservation of Original Context:** Enhancing the expression and preservation of the original context of digital and physical artefacts.
3. **Flexible Usage Policies:** Enabling the attachment of flexible usage policies to digital artefacts, allowing the project to express reuse context rules and licenses.

With the second version of this deliverable, we have completed the following future work from version one:

1. **User Alignment:**
 - a. *Original work:* the user component will be extended to align with marketplace user profiles
 - b. *Addressed through:* Deemed non-essential. The initial work was sufficient to represent Users on the marketplace.
2. **Context Elaboration:**
 - a. *Original work:* Context will be further elaborated by providing vocabularies for different classes (e.g., social movements, cultural movements)
 - b. *Addressed through:* Wikidata and AAT instances for the relevant classes are used as vocabulary terms
3. **Ontology Refinement:**
 - a. *Original work:* The ontology will be refined based on feedback from the project partners
 - b. *Addressed through:* New types physical and digital artefacts were added to reflect the domains of the pilot partners.
4. **Ontology Alignment:**
 - a. *Original work:* The ontology will be further aligned with other ontologies in the CH domain:
 - b. *Addressed through:* Ontology mapping techniques were explored and alignments were made between CACAO, Wikidata, DBpedia and EDM

Moving forward, the CACAO ontology and ARTKB will be improved based on, among others, community contributions. Specifically:

1. **Mapping to a Foundational Ontology:** The ontology will be mapped to an upper ontology, such as BFO [9] to enhance its structural coherence.
2. **Ontology Refinement:** The ontology will be refined based on feedback from the project partners, and the CH community.

3. **Knowledge Base expansion:** ARTKB will be extended with data from institutions in the project, as well as data from outside initiatives such as Europeana and DBpedia.

These improvements will be done on a continual and as-needed basis, by the original authors, the CH community and REEVALUATE partners, using open-source and as-needed contributions, in- and outside of the project.

With this work, we have enabled the expression of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management in the context of cultural heritage and developed a contextual ontology for the domain. In addition, we have provided an open, digital repository for the storage of CACAO-compliant data. Finally, we have mapped our ontology to other data models and ontologies, to connect with the broader CH community.

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	FONDAZIONE LINKS - LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY	LINKS
	FFP FILM- & FERNSEHPRODUKTION GMBH	FFP
	NUROGAMES GMBH	NURO
	GVAM GUIAS INTERACTIVAS SL	GVAM
	STIFTUNG PREUSSISCHER KULTURBESITZ	SPK
	HYPERTECH	HYP
	OLYMPIAKO MOUSEIO	OLYMPIC
	ARTHUR'S LEGAL BV	ARTHUR
	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	KU Leuven

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